

Deliverable 2.4

FUNCTIONALITY OF THE FEDERATED VERSION OF THE COHORT SELECTION SOFTWARE DEMONSTRATO

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the demonstration of the cohort selection software that will be used during the PHEMS project. Also, the chosen decentralized approach for cohort definition, discovery, and management will be presented. Different pre-study use cases for cohorts are also explained: Availability study and Feasibility study. We will also explain the use of Permit App software as a cohort management tool. The Permit App itself is described in more detail in the *Deliverable 2.5 “Decentralized system for managing research projects and data permit applications”*.

1. Introduction

The primary objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) is to establish a federated network connecting the four data controllers within the consortium. This network enables data users, including researchers, SMEs, and other innovators, to perform analytics and federated learning tasks on OMOP-modeled datasets, which remain under the control of their respective data controllers. By supporting distributed data analysis, the network fosters collaborative research while maintaining data privacy and security.

Task 2.5 in WP2 is dedicated to developing tools that allow data users to request access to cohort data across distributed OMOP databases. In parallel, Task 2.4 in WP2 aims to provide functionalities for browsing and defining cohorts tailored to the specific requirements of data users.

Specifically, **Task 2.4 Development of Metadata management and cohort selection** states the following: *“This task will build on knowledge from Task 2.1 and is responsible for creating a solution for consolidating metadata and enabling researchers to discover what data is available from data controllers. The goal is to offer an open-source research data exploration tool to support building the cohort selection which is configured to utilize federated network OMOP data. A cohort selection (e.g. set of variables, exclusion & inclusion criteria) will be stored and attached as a parameter to a data permit application.”*

To achieve these objectives, WP2 has experimented with open-source cohort browsing tools that can be utilized to provide the needed cohort browsing, cohort definition creation, and cohort definition export functionalities. The original plan was to utilize Tietoevry’s Patient Explorer software, but already early in the project it was discovered that it is not suitable for the needs of PHEMS project, and the development of the software was discontinued. An open-source tool was selected as a replacement. Despite these changes, all the original goals have remained unchanged.

1.1. The cohort definition creation tool of choice: ATLAS

The consortium and the resulting ecosystem plan to base the data management capabilities on top of the OHDSI developed OMOP Common Data Model. In addition to the OMOP CDM, the OHDSI community has developed a suite of open-source tools to support adoption and use of OMOP. Because of this, and the growing global support of the OHDSI tool stack, we chose the OHDSI ATLAS as a demonstration tool for cohort definition creation. Our approach to cohort browsing in general, and the role of the ATLAS tool is described in later chapters.

Quote from ATLAS GitHub page: *“ATLAS is an open-source software tool for researchers to conduct scientific analyses on standardized observational data converted to the OMOP Common Data Model V5. Researchers can create cohorts by defining groups of people based on exposure to a drug or diagnosis of a particular condition using healthcare claims data.”*

All these above-mentioned qualities are important for the goals set in PHEMS project, making the ATLAS a natural choice for creating and exporting cohort definitions.

2. Glossary

Table 1 ABBREVIATIONS	
TERM	DESCRIPTION
App	Application
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (an international collaborative that develops open-source tools and standards)
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (common data model for health data)
PHDS	Pediatric Health Data Space
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine, Clinical Terms (a comprehensive, multilingual clinical terminology used globally to standardize the representation of medical concepts in electronic health records)
SQL	Structured Query Language
WP	Work Package

Table 2 TERMS AND DEFINITIONS	
TERM	DESCRIPTION
ATLAS	An open-source web application for defining and analyzing cohorts using standardized health data mapped to the OMOP data model. ATLAS is developed and maintained by the OHDSI community.
Cohort	A group of individuals or data subjects identified based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria, typically defined using the OMOP common data model.

Cohort Definition	A formal specification outlining the characteristics and parameters used to select a cohort from the available datasets.
Data Controller	An organization or institution within the consortium that determines the purposes and means for processing personal data, in accordance with applicable regulations.
Data Permit	Official approval issued by a data controller, granting a data user permission to access and utilize a specified cohort for research or analytical purposes.
Data User	A person or entity, such as a researcher, SME, or innovator, who requests access to data for the purpose of conducting analytics, research, or other approved activities.
Federated Learning	A collaborative machine learning technique in which models are trained across multiple decentralized data sources, ensuring that raw data remains local, and privacy is preserved.
Permit App	A user-friendly software tool designed to facilitate the management of federated analytics and learning projects, as well as the submission and review of data permit applications.
Pre-study	A preliminary assessment to confirm that sufficient and relevant data exists within the network to support the intended research on a defined cohort.
RxNorm	A standardized clinical drug vocabulary developed by the U.S. National Library of Medicine

3. PHEMS cohort definition and discovery

Every research project must be able to define its research cohort and analyze if the participating data controllers have the required cohorts or variables which are relevant for the study. Traditionally, this is done by using various centralized tools for cohort browsing. These tools have access to patient data and allow authorized personnel to browse the variables and define cohorts based on the available data.

Traditionally cohort browsing is done using a tool, such as ATLAS. A key requirement is that the tool must be able to access a data source, which is used to construct the cohort and analyze the size of the cohort, using various combinations of variables and inclusion / exclusion criteria. As PHEMS is a decentralized data space, we aim to avoid centralized pooling of data and reliance on any single application for this. Instead, we designed a scalable, decentralized, and privacy preserving approach to discovering available cohorts, using the networks key capabilities, and enabling use of the PHDS access provider's compliant tool stacks.

In cross-border use cases, centralized pooling of data poses regulatory, operational, and privacy challenges. Cross-border transfer of patient data, and relinquishing control over data access is a big challenge and would not be easy for scalability and privacy purposes.

For this purpose, the PHEMS ecosystem does not pool patient data, or use a traditional cohort browsing tool stack. Instead, we have broken down the cohort definition, cohort discovery, and feasibility analysis into multiple steps, which include different pieces of the infrastructure.

3.1. Decentralized cohort discovery

The PHEMS approach to cohort discovery is broken down to cohort definition and pre-study steps. The cohort definition step is used to define a cohort using tools like ATLAS, and the pre-studies use the federated data processing network to validate which data controllers have large enough sample size for the cohort, to be able to partake in the study.

STEP	INPUT	TOOLS	OUTPUT
Cohort definition	Studied variables Cohort inclusion, and exclusion criteria.	Cohort definition tools (e.g. ATLAS)	Cohort definition exported in a supported format
Availability pre-study	Cohort definition	Data Permit App PHEMS federated network	List of data controllers with binary result on whether they have availability of data according to the cohort definition
Feasibility pre-study	Cohort definition	Data Permit App PHEMS federated network	Data controller -specific results, providing range of available rows

The image below describes on a very high level the basic concept of pre-studies. The federated data processing network is used to make standardized analytics queries to the participating network hospitals. First, these queries are planned to be executed manually by PHEMS consortium data controller personnel only and later by data users themselves. The availability pre-study query is limited to providing binary yes/no -responses, whereas the feasibility pre-study query enables hospitals to define the range which they respond with. Using this method, the research project can define cohorts and discover which hospitals can provide adequate data for the actual research project.

Figure 1 CONCEPT DESCRIPTION OF THE PRE-STUDIES.

3.2. Cohort definition

Discovery of available data is done by collecting metadata from the data controller’s OMOP databases, for example in the form of OHDSI data quality report and creating an aggregated view on the PHDS access provider platform. This means that the PHDS access provider can construct a dataset, which resembles the available data in the PHEMS ecosystem, without revealing accurate patient data. This type of data is not in itself very useful for other purposes than testing the design of the cohort and providing input into which variables and criteria may be used for the cohort definition design.

The purpose is to provide the researcher with understanding of which OMOP variables and criteria can be used with each data controller. It does not yet help to discover if the cohort design returns adequate simple size, as there is no access to real data sources.

3.3. Availability pre-study

Availability study enables to determine which data controllers in the PHEMS network hold the combination of patient data that that is relevant for the research topic in question. This will allow the researcher to create a shortlist of data controllers, who could possibly participate in the study.

Availability study utilizes the PHEMS Federated Network to perform pre-study with all the data controllers. An availability pre-study is a trusted and pre-verified algorithm, that includes the cohort definition provided by the researcher. The algorithm returns a binary yes / no response from each data controller. The binary response indicates if the data controller’s patient database can produce at least minimum amount of result rows for the provided cohort definition.

3.4. Feasibility study

Feasibility study enables to determine the approximate number of records available from data controllers for the research cohort. It utilizes the PHEMS Federated Network to make a pre-study with

a selected subset of data controllers. A feasibility pre-study uses a trusted and pre-verified algorithm, and a cohort definition provided by the researcher.

Each data controller returns a range, indicating a rough estimate of how many records the cohort request produces. Results are ranges, for example “over 100”, “between 100 and 1000”, or “less than 100”. This type of pre-study can be processed either automatically or manually, but it is expected that each data controller employs verification mechanisms to prevent misuse, accidental or purposeful threshold discovery using “curious query” mechanisms.

4. Set up for the demonstration

This section presents a step-by-step demonstration of the intended cohort browsing capabilities, illustrating its intended use by data users within the daily operations of the PHEMS Federated Network. The demonstration will be delivered as a part of a larger video recording produced by Tietoevry, with the initial presentation scheduled for the consortium meeting in Rotterdam in June 2025.

4.1. Access cohort browsing tool

In PHEMS project, data users conduct their research through research workspaces. Workspaces are hosted and maintained by PHDS access providers, which can be, for example, companies offering such services or data controllers. These workspaces will also include the cohort browsing tools, where local copies are hosted. Data users can access those tools after logging into the workspace.

4.2. Access the dataset

For the purposes of our demo, we are using a publicly available demo dataset called Synthea [EunomiaDatasets/datasets/Synthea27Nj at main · OHDSI/EunomiaDatasets · GitHub](#). This dataset enables us to define an example cohort and export it. Later in the project when aggregated real-world data from data controllers is available at PHDS access providers workspaces, it will be used instead.

4.3. Browsing the dataset and defining a cohort

This section describes the process of constructing a cohort definition using the ATLAS tool. The workflow supports standardized cohort creation across datasets that conform to the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM), enabling consistent and reproducible observational research in a federated data environment.

The process of cohort creation is described in detail in The Book of OHDSI (Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics [OHDSI], 2021).

4.3.1. Initiating a new cohort

The cohort definition process begins by selecting the “New Cohort” option in ATLAS. A meaningful name and optional metadata are provided to describe the cohort’s purpose and context.

4.3.2. Specifying entry events

Cohort entry is based on clinical events that qualify individuals for inclusion. These events are selected from OMOP CDM domains such as *Condition Occurrence*, *Drug Exposure*, or *Procedure Occurrence*. A concept set — comprising standardized vocabulary codes (e.g., SNOMED CT, RxNorm) — is created or reused to represent the clinical meaning of the entry event. Temporal logic can be applied to define the timing of events relative to other occurrences.

4.3.3. Applying inclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria are used to further restrict the cohort population based on demographic or clinical characteristics. These may include age, gender, prior observation time, or the presence or absence of specific conditions or treatments. Logical expressions combine multiple criteria as needed.

4.3.4. Defining exit criteria

Cohort exit is determined by specifying when individuals should no longer be considered part of the cohort. Exit rules may be based on a fixed duration following cohort entry, the occurrence of a specific event, or the end of the individual's observation period.

4.3.5. Finalizing the cohort definition

Once all components have been configured, the cohort definition is reviewed for completeness and logical consistency. The finalized definition is saved within ATLAS and can be used for cohort generation or exported for use in other tools or analytical workflows.

4.4. Exporting cohort

After its creation, the cohort definition can be exported in formats such as SQL or JSON.

SQL is used to execute the cohort definition directly against a database that follows the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM). JSON is a good alternative if the goal is to save or share the cohort definition in a structured, machine-readable format.

4.5. Importing the cohort into Permit App

Exported cohort definitions can be imported into the Permit App, where they can be attached to a data permit application. Additionally, pre-studies can be launched for selected cohorts. These functionalities will be covered in detail in Deliverable 2.5 “Decentralized system for managing research projects and data permit applications”.

5. Conclusions

The demonstration of the cohort selection software highlights its effectiveness in supporting decentralized cohort management capabilities required by the federated network. A secure, widely adopted and user-friendly open-source tool for cohort definition reaction ensures that the federated network can easily be scaled in the future, and cohort management tools will stay up to date. The functionalities described in this deliverable contribute to the overall objectives of the project, fostering innovation and responsible data use within the federation network.

List of references

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